

Optimization of phenol removal from aqueous solutions using fly ash obtained from power station as adsorbent : Kinetic and equilibrium studies

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Manuscript received online 19 February 2014, revised 13 April 2014, accepted 15 April 2014

Abstract : Phenols are toxic chemicals affect living organisms even at lower concentrations. Reduction of phenol concentrations to the permissible regulatory level is therefore important for wastewater treatment engineers. In this study, batch adsorption experiments were conducted to investigate the removal of phenol from aqueous solution using an industrial solid waste fly ash. Experimental parameters such as initial pH, initial phenol concentrations, adsorbent dosage and adsorbent-adsorbate contact time affecting phenol removal efficiency were investigated, optimized and compared with activated carbon. Different adsorption models were used to describe the adsorption kinetics, establish the corresponding rate constants and predict the theoretical adsorption capacities of adsorbents. It is suggested that fly ash is a potential effectual adsorbent for the removal of phenol from aqueous solution.

Keywords : Phenol, adsorption, fly ash, activated carbon, industrial solid waste.

Introduction

Phenols due to their toxic nature are regarded as priority pollutants and affect living organisms in the environment even at lower concentrations¹⁻⁴. Phenols are discharged into the environment through industrial effluents, agricultural runoff and chemical spillage. The industries responsible for the discharge of effluents containing phenols are petrochemicals, pesticides, steel, rubber industries, coke plants, etc.⁵⁻⁹. Widely adopted technologies for the removal of phenols from aqueous solutions are coagulation, froth flotation, chemical oxidation and adsorption^{10,11}. Adsorption using activated carbon is considered as an established method for the successful reduction of phenol concentrations from aqueous solutions. It is often used in the tertiary wastewater treatment stage for polishing incoming influent before final discharge into water bodies^{12,13}. Though activated carbon is a highly effectual adsorbent, many researchers are currently focusing their efforts on utilizing reusable solid waste materials. One such material is industrial fly ash which may originate from combustion of solid materials such as bio-

mass. Several researchers showed keen interest in utilizing the fly ash as an adsorbent for the adsorption of phenolic compounds and observed that fly ash has a good adsorption potential towards phenolic compounds^{5,14,15}. Khanna and Malhotra¹⁴ were the first to examine the phenol removal by fly ash and the data provided by them were successfully adopted in the design of phenol-fly ash adsorption systems.

In this study an attempt has been made to utilize an industrial solid waste such as fly ash as an adsorbent. The adsorption capacity of fly ash for phenol adsorption from aqueous solutions was investigated and compared with activated carbon. Different adsorption models were used to describe the adsorption kinetics, establish the corresponding rate constants and predict the theoretical adsorption capacities of adsorbents. The use of fly ash originating from an Indian power station, an industrial waste in itself, as a novel phenolic adsorbent also assists in alleviating disposal problem of such solid waste in Asian countries.

*Materials and methods :**Adsorbents :*

Fly ash was collected from Raichur thermal power station situated at *ca.* 20 km north of Raichur, Karnataka, India. The fly ash was collected from the electrostatic precipitator and used without any pretreatment. Commercially available activated carbon (Merck India Limited) was purchased and used without any pretreatment for comparison purpose. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Zeiss Supra 55 PP) together with energy dispersive X-ray (EDX) spectroscopy (Oxford INCA) were used to analyse the surface morphology (Fig. 1) and elemental composition of the fly ash, respectively. The chemical composition of fly ash was identified using X-ray fluorescence spectrometer (XRF) (Philips PW2400) and summarized in Table 1. It is observed that the ash particles are spherical in shape, an observation similar to previous SEM observations for fly ash¹⁶.

Reagents :

The primary chemicals used in the study : phenol (Merck India Limited), 4-amino antipyrine (Reachem India Limited), ammonia solution (Nice Chemicals India Limited) and potassium ferricyanide (Nice Chemicals India Limited) were of analytical reagent (AR) grade. Stock solution of phenol (1000 mg/L) was prepared by dissolving 1000 mg of phenol in 1 L of double distilled water. Desired concentrations of phenol were prepared by dilution of the appropriate quantity of the above stock solution for each adsorption study.

Batch adsorption experiments :

The batch adsorption experiments were conducted in 250 mL conical flasks using 100 mL of known concentration of phenol solution. Solution pH was adjusted to the desired value and a measured quantity of adsorbent was added. The contents in the flasks were agitated immediately using rotary shaker. The flasks were kept sealed throughout the experiment. The contents in the flasks were drawn at regular intervals of time, filtered with Whatman No. 42 filter paper and concentration of phenol

Fig. 1 SEM micrographs of the fly ash.

Table 1. Chemical composition of fly ash

Constituent	SiO ₂	Al ₂ O ₃	CaO	Fe ₂ O ₃	MgO	SO ₃	TiO ₂	P ₂ O ₅	Na ₂ O	Mn ₃ O ₄	K ₂ O
Mass (%)	63.55	22.71	5.66	3.72	1.48	1.34	0.60	0.46	0.26	0.16	0.11

in the filtrate was analyzed by spectrophotometric analysis method¹⁷ using UV-Vis spectrophotometer (Elico-BL 198). In order to investigate effects of parameters such as pH, initial phenol concentration, adsorbent quantity and agitation time on phenol removal, batch adsorption experiments were conducted by following an approach of varying one variable at a time (OVAT).

Results and discussion

A series of batch experiments were carried out to investigate the effects of initial pH, initial phenol concentration, adsorbent dosage and agitation time on phenol removal by fly ash and the results were compared with activated carbon.

Effect of initial pH :

Initial pH of aqueous solution is one of the critical factors affecting removal efficiency of phenol and it is necessary to identify the best pH range at which the maximum phenol removal occurs. A series of experiments were conducted at an initial pH range of 2 to 8 whereas, initial phenol concentration, adsorbent dosage and agitation time were maintained constant as 30 mg/L, 2 g/L, and 3 h, respectively for both the adsorbents. The effect of initial pH on phenol removal efficiency is depicted in Fig. 2. It was observed that phenol removal efficiency was 48.29% and 93.24% for fly ash and activated carbon, respectively at pH 2. Increase in pH resulted in an

increase in phenol removal efficiency and attained a maximum removal (70% and 98.60%) for fly ash and activated carbon at pH 4 and 6, respectively. Further increase in pH resulted in decrease in phenol removal efficiency. Phenol has a pKa value of 9.89 and it dissociates at $\text{pH} > \text{pKa}$. The increase in pH results in the ionization of phenol molecules and results in decrease in phenol adsorption⁹.

Effect of initial concentrations :

In order to investigate the adsorption capacity of fly ash at different initial phenol concentrations, experiments were conducted at different initial phenol concentrations, 10 to 60 mg/L at an agitation period of 3 h. Adsorbent dosage and pH were kept as 2 g/L and 4, respectively. Experiments were also conducted using activated carbon at an optimum pH of 6 and adsorbent dosage and agitation time were kept similar to fly ash experiments. Fig. 3 shows the effect of initial concentration on phenol removal by both fly ash and activated carbon. It can be seen from Fig. 3 that phenol removal efficiency increased with an increase in initial concentration up to 30 mg/L and decreased with further increase in initial phenol concentration for both the adsorbents. Activated carbon achieved more than 90% removal efficiency for an initial phenol concentrations ranging from 10 to 60 mg/L and maximum removal efficiency, 98.60% was obtained at 30 mg/L whereas for fly ash it was 70%.

Fig. 2. Effect of initial pH on phenol removal efficiency by fly ash and activated carbon.

Fig. 3. Effect of initial phenol concentrations on phenol removal efficiency by fly ash and activated carbon.

Effect of adsorbent dosage :

The adsorption capacity of the adsorbent depends upon the adsorbent dosage. Effect of adsorbent dosage on phenol removal by fly ash was studied by varying adsorbent quantity from 1 to 5 g/L and agitating the aqueous solution for 3 h. Initial phenol concentration and pH were maintained constant as 30 mg/L and 4, respectively. Adsorption experiments were also conducted using activated carbon for comparison purpose. The effect of adsorbent dosage on phenol removal by fly ash and activated carbon is shown in Fig. 4. Phenol adsorption capacity of fly ash was increased from 34.26 to 70.03% when adsorbent

quantity was increased from 1 to 2 g/L. This is due to the increased surface area and availability of more binding sites. The increase in phenol removal efficiency was negligible with further increase in adsorbent quantity from 2 to 5 g/L indicating the depletion of phenol ions present at 30 mg/L aqueous phenol solution even though sufficient binding sites of adsorbent were available. Phenol removal by activated carbon was more than 90% and maximum removal of 98.60% was achieved at 2 g/L of adsorbent quantity (Fig. 4).

Effect of contact time :

Optimum contact time for maximum phenol removal

Fig. 4. Effect of adsorbent dosage on phenol removal by fly ash and activated carbon.

Fig. 5. Effect of contact time on phenol removal by fly ash and activated carbon.

by fly ash and activated carbon was determined by agitating the aqueous solution of phenol and adsorbent (2 g/L) for different time intervals between 15 and 240 min at pH 4 and 6 for fly ash and activated carbon, respectively (Fig. 5). Phenol removal of 82.50% was achieved at 15 min agitation and maximum removal of 98.60% was achieved at 90 min of contact and thereafter remained constant indicating the saturation of adsorbent binding sites. Maximum removal of 70% was achieved by fly ash on 180 min and thereafter the removal efficiency remained almost constant.

Optimum parameters (pH, initial concentration, adsorbent dosage and contact time) for removal of phenol from aqueous solution by fly ash and activated carbon are tabulated in Table 2.

Kinetic studies and adsorption isotherms :

Kinetic studies :

The efficiency of the adsorption process is evaluated by the adsorption kinetic study as it furnishes the valuable information about the adsorption mechanism¹⁸. The dynamics of phenol adsorption on fly ash and activated carbon were studied by the kinetics of adsorption by means of the order of the rate constant. A fast and effective model can be designed by carrying out investigations on adsorption rate using pseudo-first order Lagergren and pseudo-second order kinetic models. The pseudo kinetic

Table 2. Optimum parameters for the removal of phenol by fly ash and activated carbon at an initial phenol concentration, 30 mg/L

Adsorbents	pH	Adsorbent dosage (g/L)	Contact time (min)
Fly ash	4	2	180
Activated carbon	6	2	90

models were chosen because the mass action rate equation for adsorption kinetics as a chemical phenomenon and a diffusion equation for diffusion through a boundary liquid film are similar to the pseudo-first order rate equation of Lagergren¹⁹.

Pseudo-first order Lagergren equation is represented as²⁰

$$\log (q_e - q) = \log q_e - \frac{K_1 t}{2.303} \tag{1}$$

where q is amount of adsorbate adsorbed (mg/g) at time t , q_e is amount adsorbed (mg/g) at equilibrium time and K_1 pseudo-first order rate constant (min^{-1}). q_e and K_1 can be calculated from the slopes and the intercept of the plot $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t . Linear plot of $\log (q_e - q)$ vs t of fly ash and activated carbon at initial phenol concentration, 30 mg/L is shown in Fig. 6. Pseudo-first order rate constants obtained for both the adsorbents along with correlation coefficient (R^2) are summarized in Table 3.

Fig. 6. Pseudo-first order kinetics for adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon.

Pseudo-second order equation is¹⁹

$$\frac{t}{q} = \frac{1}{K_2 q_e^2} + \frac{t}{q_e} \quad (2)$$

where K_2 is pseudo-second order rate constant ($\text{g mg}^{-1} \text{min}^{-1}$). Fig. 7 depicts linear plot of t/q vs t of both adsorbents at an initial phenol concentration of 30 mg/L. Pseudo-second order rate constants along with R^2 value for both the adsorbents are tabulated in Table 4. The experimental and pseudo-second order model estimated values of q_e were found to have a good agreement with R^2 values of 0.95 and 0.99 for fly ash and activated carbon, respectively. Whereas the pseudo-first order Lagergren model estimated q_e values do not agree with the experimental q_e values although R^2 values can reach up to 0.94 and 0.93 for fly ash and activated carbon, respectively (Table 3) indicating that the adsorption of phenol on both these adsorbents do not conform to the pseudo-first order model.

Adsorption isotherms :

The two well known adsorption isotherm models viz.

Langmuir and Freundlich were used to investigate the adsorption capacity of phenol by fly ash and activated carbon. The linear form of Langmuir equation is²¹

$$\frac{c_e}{q_e} = \frac{1}{Q_0 b} + \frac{c_e}{Q_0} \quad (3)$$

where c_e is equilibrium concentration of adsorbate (mg/L), q_e is amount adsorbed at equilibrium time (mg/g), Q_0 is adsorption capacity (mg/g) and b is constant (L/mg). The adsorption capacity of the adsorbent Q_0 and constant b can be calculated from the slope and intercept of the linear plot of c_e/q_e vs c_e . The Langmuir adsorption can be expressed based on a dimensionless constant, R_L . The values of R_L between 0 and 1 indicate favorable adsorption.

The linear form of Freundlich model is expressed as²² :

$$\log q_e = \log k_f + \frac{1}{n} \log c_e \quad (4)$$

where k_f is adsorption capacity of adsorbent (mg/g) and n is constant. Values of n between 1 and 10 indicate favor-

Table 3. Pseudo-first order kinetic model parameters for the adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon

Adsorbent	q_e , experiment (mg/g)	Pseudo-first order kinetic model constants		
		K_1 (min^{-1})	q_e (mg/g)	R^2
Fly ash	21.0	0.018	26.92	0.94
Activated carbon	29.58	0.035	10.03	0.93

Fig. 7. Pseudo-second order kinetics for adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon.

Table 4. Pseudo-second order kinetic model parameters for the adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon

Adsorbent	q_e , experiment (mg/g)	Pseudo-second order kinetic model constants		
		K_2 (g/mg) min ⁻¹	q_e (mg/g)	R^2
Fly ash	21.0	0.001	24.39	0.95
Activated carbon	29.58	0.013	30.03	0.99

able adsorption.

Figs. 8 and 9 show the linear plot of c_e/q_e vs c_e (Langmuir) for phenol adsorption onto fly ash and activated carbon, respectively. The Langmuir constants, val-

ues of R_L along with R^2 are tabulated in Table 5. R_L values between 0 and 1 indicate the favorable adsorption of phenol by both the adsorbents. Table 6 shows the Freundlich constants along with R^2 values for both the

Fig. 8. The linear Langmuir adsorption isotherm for phenol with fly ash.

Fig. 9. The linear Langmuir adsorption isotherm for phenol with activated carbon.

Table 5. Langmuir constants for the adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon

Adsorbent	Initial phenol concentration (mg/L)	R_L	Langmuir constants		
			Q_o (mg/g)	b (L/mg)	R^2
Fly ash	20	0.15	7.68	0.28	0.84
	30	0.11			
	40	0.08			
	60	0.06			
Activated carbon	10	0.12	34.60	0.76	0.91
	20	0.06			
	30	0.04			
	40	0.03			
	60	0.02			

adsorbents. The equilibrium adsorption data was satisfactorily fitted with Langmuir isotherm model as compared with Freundlich model based on R^2 values. It is widely known that the Langmuir adsorption isotherm assumes that adsorption occurs at specific sites within the adsorbent²¹. Therefore, once the adsorbate occupies a site, no further adsorption will take place at that site^{21,23}.

Table 6. Freundlich constants for the adsorption of phenol onto fly ash and activated carbon

Adsorbent	Freundlich constants		
	k_f (mg/g)	n	R^2
Fly ash	1.06	1.90	0.3
Activated carbon	1.40	2.12	0.7

Conclusions

The utility and viability of fly ash as adsorbent for removal of phenol using synthetic samples is investigated. The optimal conditions for phenol removal were studied. It was observed that the optimum removal occurs at an initial phenol concentration of 30 mg/L, at pH, 4 with an adsorbent dosage of 2 g/L and maximum agitation time of 180 min. The kinetics of phenol adsorption by fly ash is better explained by the pseudo-second order kinetic model. The equilibrium adsorption data was satisfactorily fitted with Langmuir isotherm model.

Acknowledgements

The authors gratefully thank KLE Dr. M. S. Sheshgiri College of Engineering and Technology, Belgaum, Karnataka, India for providing the facilities for conducting this research. The authors extend their appreciation to the Deanship of Scientific Research at King Saud University for funding this work through research group no. RGP-VPP-303.

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Deshannavar *et al.* : Optimization of phenol removal from aqueous solutions using fly ash *etc.*

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